

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN**¹Kamolov Dostonbek Rustam ugli, ²Qilicheva Rukhshona Sherbota kizi¹Teacher of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan.²Student of Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan.**РАЗВИТИЕ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**¹Камалов Достонбек Рустам угли, ²Кылычева Рухшана Щербота кызы¹Преподаватель Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана.²Студент Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана.**O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISH**¹Kamolov Dostonbek Rustam o'g'li, ²Qilicheva Ruxshona Sherbo'ta qizi¹O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali o'qituvchisi.²O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali talabasi.**abstract**

The article will talk about small business and private entrepreneurship, which are the main sectors that develop the economy, and about the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

аннотация

В статье рассказывается о малом бизнесе и частном предпринимательстве, которые являются основными секторами экономики, а также о развитии малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства.

annotatsiya

Maqolada iqtisodiyotni rivojlantiruvchi asosiy tarmoqlar bo'lgan kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik haqida hamda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanishi haqida so'z boradi.

Keywords:

small business, private enterprise, employment of the population, income, credit, budget income, microenterprises.

Ключевые слова:

малый бизнес, частное предпринимательство, занятость, доход, кредит, доходы бюджета, микрофирмы.

Kalit so'zlar:

Kichik biznes, xususiy tadbirkorlik, aholi bandligi, daromad, kredit, byudjet daromadlari, mikrofirmalar.

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Introduction

During the years of independence, it is necessary to note the creation of a stable legislative base in Uzbekistan, which strengthens the priority of private property, which is the basis of the market economy. A favorable business environment and reliable legal guarantees for the rapid development of small business and private

entrepreneurship have been created, which is an important factor in the formation of a middle owner class, the sustainable development of the country's economy, the creation of new jobs and the increase in the income of the population.

As a result, in the last ten years, the share of small businesses in the structure of GDP has increased from 31.1% to 52.5%, the employment rate in this area has increased from 49.7% to 74.5% of the total number of employed residents in sectors of the economy. More than 47% of the population's income corresponds to the contribution of income from entrepreneurial activity.

Analysis and discussions

In accordance with the state program "Year of small business and private entrepreneurship", comprehensive measures have been adopted in this year to create a more favorable business environment for the widespread development of entrepreneurial activity. The procedure for state registration of business entities and their connection to engineering and communication networks has been significantly simplified, and this process has gained more openness. The state duty rate for registration was reduced by two times. The list of types of activities that small businesses can engage in, in which the annual average number of workers is increased to 100 people, has been significantly expanded. A mechanism was developed and introduced to involve small business entities in the public procurement process on a large scale.

Measures were adopted to dramatically reduce the interference of state and control agencies in the financial and economic activities of enterprises and to significantly expand the economic freedom and rights of business entities. The deadline for exempting newly established small businesses and microfirms from scheduled tax inspections was extended from two to three years. In small business entities paying taxes and other mandatory fees on time, as well as ensuring stable growth rates and profitability of production, it was forbidden to carry out tax checks for three years.

The level of capitalization of commercial banks is increasing, the mechanism of preferential lending for small business entities, especially their purchase of high-tech equipment, has been improved.

At the same time, a number of problems that are hindering the rapid development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, limiting the freedom of entrepreneurial activity, remain unresolved.

An administrative regulation has not been fully developed that clearly defines the interaction of business entities with state, tax and control agencies, commercial banks. Many permitting procedures, whose openness is not ensured, still remain. There are cases of illegal interference in the activities of business entities of control agencies.

No practical mechanism has been created to bring small business products to the regional and world markets.

In order to further radically improve the business environment, move intensively on the path of liberalization and deepening market reforms, give more freedom to entrepreneurship, eliminate obstacles and gaps in the path to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, increase the role and share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country's economy, develop export potential, provide employment and income:

-implementation of specific measures to eliminate excessive bureaucratic barriers and pitfalls on the path to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, reduce the functions of Public Administration and give more freedom to entrepreneurship, sharply reduce the various permitting norms and restriction procedures carried out by public administration bodies;

-to ensure openness and transparency in the interaction of business entities with public administration agencies, tax and control structures, to radically simplify the reporting system and the mechanism for submitting reports to financial, tax and statistical offices by going through a step-by-step transition to their submission by electronic system;

- to provide additional benefits and preferences to small businesses and private business entities that promote the rapid development of entrepreneurial activity in tax, customs and other payments and increase its efficiency;

-to further improve and simplify the mechanism of interaction of small business and private business entities with commercial banks, to improve the quality of service to business entities, to increase the volume of loans allocated to them, first of all, to organize new production facilities, to modernize existing production facilities and to increase the volume of long-term loans aimed at technological;

-to create favorable conditions for the wide participation of small businesses and private business entities in foreign economic activities, to promote their products to foreign markets, to simplify and liberalize the registration process of export contracts and Customs Administration in general.

-The principle of the priority of Entrepreneurs ' Rights in the interaction of entities of entrepreneurial activity with public administration agencies of all levels, law enforcement and control bodies, commercial banks is followed, that is, in accordance with it, all irreplaceable conflicts and uncertainties in regulatory legal acts are interpreted in favor of entrepreneurs;

- limit the period of consideration by commercial banks of applications of small business and private business entities for the allocation of loans in the agreed volume by a period not exceeding three bank days;

- equating payment terminal checks to primary accounting documents when making payments using corporate plastic cards for goods (work, services) purchased by business entities in the field of trade and service;

- granting small business and private business entities the right to independently transfer cash receipts to banking institutions.

Economic entities were exempted from paying customs duties (except customs clearance fees) until January 1, 2016 for spare and components brought to the territory of the Republic on a list approved by the Cabinet of ministers on the installed technological equipment.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan introduced in one month the draft laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on amendments and additions to the legislative acts providing for the following.

lifting sanctions not related to the calculation of taxes and other mandatory payments for legal entities, at the same time doubling the administrative liability of officials of economic entities who committed repeated violations;

limitation of the period of customs control by three years, as well as a year after the transfer of goods from customs control, a ban on the additional calculation of customs duties.

In cooperation with the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of finance, the Ministry of foreign economic relations, investments and trade of the Ministry of justice, within a month a proposal was made to the Cabinet of Ministers on amendments and additions arising from this decree.

The development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

The comprehensive measures carried out to further improve the business environment in our republic, ensure reliable protection of small business and private entrepreneurship, support them in every possible way and eliminate the obstacles on the path of rapid development made it possible to organize 31,766 new small business entities (in addition to peasant and farmer households) during 2016. As a result, the number of small business entities operating as of January 1, 2017 is 218,170, increasing to 11,066 compared to the same period of the year of shooting.

As a result of creating more favorable conditions for small business and private business entities, their share in the country's GDP is 56.9 percent (56.5 percent in January-December 2015), in the industry-45.0 percent (40.6 percent), in the services sector-60.5 percent (57.8 percent), in exports-28.5 percent (27.0 percent) and in

employment-78.1 percent 77.9 percent). In January-December 2016, 19963.2 billion was allocated to the economy by the subjects of small business and private enterprise. Some investments were made. This represents 40.3% of the total investment in the Republic. They also received Rs 20,677.7 crore. Some construction work was carried out (70.7% of the total volume of construction work) or increased by 15.6% compared to the same period of the year of shooting.

Conclusion

At the moment, this sector occupies a leading place not only in accelerating the growth rates of the economy, but also in solving the issues of increasing employment and population income, which are extremely important for our country. Therefore, it is considered important for small business entities to study activities and research ways to solve existing attitudes in the field and improve their effectiveness.

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